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WORK CULTURE AS A COMPONENT OF FUTURE LABOUR TEACHERS' CULTURE

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У статті охарактеризовано культуру праці як один зі складників культури людини, окреслено важливість трудової підготовки у формуванні культури праці учня. Розглянуто різні наукові підходи сучасних учених до поняття «культура праці». Окреслено основні ідеї трудового виховання видатних українських педагогів А.С. Макаренка та В.О. Сухомлинського, що є актуальними у сучасній педагогічній практиці. Визначено основні вектори формування культури праці, обґрунтовані державним стандартом освітньої галузі «Технології», що дозволяють з'ясувати структуру підготовки майбутнього вчителя технологій та наповнити ринок праці компетентними фахівцями, здатними забезпечувати якісний процес трудового навчання, що сприятиме формуванню культури праці школярів.

Ключові слова: культура, культура праці, особистість, технологічна освіта.

The term «culture» (from lat. cultura – agriculture, upbringing, education, respect). This concept has a great number of meanings in different fields. In general, under the term culture we understand human activity associated with the expression of personality, a manifestation of his subjectivity (behavior, personality, competence, knowledge and skills) [6].

Culture also characterizes the features of consciousness, behavior and activities of people in specific areas of public life (work culture, economic culture, the culture of training activities, information culture). Culture is the subject of study of many sciences – Philosophy, Culturology, Sociology, Pedagogics, Psychology etc.

Culture is a specific characteristic of society, and expresses a level of historical development achieved by humanity, which includes a certain attitude of a man towards nature, labor and society, as well as the development of creative forces and abilities of the individual. It includes not only the subject results of human activity (machines, technical facilities, works of

art, norms of law and morality), but also subjective human forces and capabilities, realized in activity (worldview, knowledge and skills, production and professional skills, experience, level of intellectual, aesthetic and moral development, methods and forms of mutual people's communication in the collectivity and society).

It is necessary to note that among the main problems of the present the culture education of the young generation is one of the most important. The solution of this problem the society traditionally imposes on a secondary school because the pedagogical higher education performs a cultural function, which involves updating the content on the basis of its humanitarization, purposeful use of the achievements of Ukrainian culture. Numerous scientific publications that have appeared in recent years suggest that the search for solution of cultural problems of modern education is gradually gaining wide scope. Thus, cultural components are characterized by K. Ivanov, V. Lyhvar, E. Podolska; issues of multiculturalism are outlined in the works of K. Irvine, M. Krasovytskyi; psychological and pedagogical aspects are reflected in the works of S. Zhuravlia, V. Strumanskyi; the methodical aspects of formation of work culture in the work activity are revealed by V. Avramenko, Yu. Kuzmenko, S. Lisova, S. Tkachuk, etc.

The purpose of this article is to consider the work culture as an integral part of the culture of the individual.

The education of the person's culture takes the whole life. The main burden of implementing the model of the fully developed person's culture, of course, rests with the school. The primary source of the formation of the culture of the child is the family, which lays the basic components of cultural identity. This happens in the course of the observations the members of the family, their relations to the society in general, and inclusion of the child in the process of vital activity of the family. Education should help people to identify its main values, to internalize moral norms, everyday ethics, namely to understand everyday culture formation.

The content of culture is a reflection of social reality, and scientific and technical progress requires us to rethink the trends related to it from the point of view of harmonious development of personality.

Since ancient times, philosophers and teachers have permanently created a model of «cultural person», which included qualities and meaningful personality traits.

One of the components of person's culture was always the culture of work, which according to the conditions and realities of the present day is of particular significance.

Butenko L. draws attention to the fact that the problems of the general culture of a person was repeatedly investigated in the theory and practice of pedagogical science, as the qualities of the cultural person and the requirements for the culture of the individual and the process of education is very diverse [2]. Butenko L. proves that culture should be understood as the level of education of the person and the level of mastering the relevant abilities and skills, namely a high level of professionalism. The scientist draws attention to the fact that the person who is engaged in self-education, cultivating talent, committed to self-knowledge, self-esteem, self-improvement, inner growth, spiritual integrity, is a man of high culture.

The work culture of personality describes his/her attitude to work, moral and psychological preparedness, intellectual ability and emotional and volitional qualities. And his/her motivational component is based on needs, preferences and interests, in a word, on the whole system of values that define the socio-psychological orientation of the personality. Objectively the culture is evident in the attitude to labor, its products, tools, working people and so on. It is worth to note that the work culture should be considered as a factor that generates the appropriate needs of the person. Everything valuable that mankind has created, that they have preserved for their descendants, exists because of physical and mental work of people.

It is not only material objects and activities to create home appliances and housing, but also works of art, the experience of people's life organization in different historical periods, various types of communication, speech development and so on.

It is known that today the purposeful process of formation of students' culture of labor in the learning process is not specifically performed, and it occurs only in accordance with the purposes of training and education in the training of mental work. The bases for the formation of culture are all subjects in secondary school. One of the most effective ways of formation of students' culture of work is labor training. It was repeatedly pointed out by such scholars as D. Zembytskyi, N. Pobirchenko, V. Sydorenko, N. Sliusarenko, V. Strumanskyi, G. Tereshchuk, S. Tkachuk, D. Tkhorzhevskyi and others.

In the educational environment has been increasingly adopted the opinion on the application of cultural approach to technological education with the aim of further improvement. According to the scientist T. Machacha, «the development of the system of technological preparation of students involves the creation of conditions for realization of creative potential of each student with the aim of self-realization and self-determination; the structuring of the content of the subject according to its cultural, integrative, synergetic, concentric principles; the creation of a culture of transforming activity, which is aimed at creating material and spiritual values in the various fields of activity and is necessary for any specialist» [6, p. 26].

It should be noted that the implementation of the new curriculum on labor education for secondary schools requires that teachers today have the ability to solve entirely new problems, in particular the formation of pupils' culture. The essence of pupils' labor training, as one of the leading aspects of the labor culture is determined by the purpose, the major tasks, content, methods and forms of its organization. These elements of the pedagogical system have found their coverage in scientific works. In particular, recent studies of the process of formation of students' culture of secondary school in the process of labor training were conducted by V. Avramenko, Yu. Kuzmenko, S. Syvashchenko. Scientists take into account socio-economic changes in the country, the condition of reforming of the general secondary education, in particular the educational area «Technologies», as well as the content and provisions of the new program of labor training. Researcher A. Avramenko said that the students' work culture is a complex personal education, which expresses the level of mastering of a certain system of knowledge and skills of their application in practical activities [1].

Kuzmenko Y. the concept of «work culture of a student» understands «as a set of formed cultural qualities of a person, which is based on a conscious assimilation, the preservation and enhancement by the student specialized knowledge, skills and experience contributing to the effectiveness of views and beliefs» [4, c. 20].

S. Syvashchenko notes that «in the first place, the culture of work mainly covers the qualitative aspect of educational labor activity. In the second place, in the educational labor activity the work culture is seen primarily as a goal, not as a mean. In the third place, the implementation of practical task in the course of labor activity provides the formation and improvement of the work culture. And, in the fourth place, the work culture in fact as an integral component of general culture is the cultural dimension of «live» work, which in itself has value and importance and also defines the intangible value of results of labor activity. Learning labor activity has a valuable dimension and is primarily characterized by metrics of labor culture» [3].

Thus, the analysis of different approaches to the definition of «work culture», published in the scientific literature, suggests that many generations of scientists and teachers-practitioners have interest in cultural problems of upbringing and education. It can be seen and today, due to the need to solve the problems which are associated with increasing level of youth culture, with cultural identity formation in our society and the formation of a work culture.

An important step in the development of ideas in the formation of the youth culture is considered to be 20th years of the twentieth century, when there was a rapid development of

industrial production. Technical progress required well-trained, qualified, scientifically-trained workers.

Outstanding teacher A. Makarenko paid much attention to the formation of the youth the ability to organize and plan their work, to observe the rules of behavior and to ensure a business environment, abilities and skills quickly, efficiently and in a timely manner to perform duties during their pedagogical work. He believed that work activity should be the basis of life of the youth team and that the team work under the able guidance of a teacher shapes the elements of work culture that will be useful to youth in their future independent life [2].

To the problems of the work culture addressed a famous Ukrainian teacher V. Sukhomlynskyi. In the unity of the work culture and the overall harmonious development of personality, he saw one of the fundamental principles of labor education. He said that no matter how high level has reached the technical idea, the road to academic heights and work culture will go through mastering the alphabet of technique, by which he understands the ability to read technical documentation, knowledge of simple tools, devices and mechanisms. Harmonious, comprehensive development, education, spiritual wealth, moral purity – all this man reaches only when, together with intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical culture, achieves a high degree of work culture of the labor of creativity [4].

Work culture regarding classes on labor education is the ability to plan their work, considering it as a part of work activity of the whole team; to keep clean your working place and efficiently use tools and materials; work quickly and accurately, adhering to the correct working posture and using rational methods of labor; to perform high-quality work-study tasks; accurately and in accordance with the requirements set by the period of training, to make products; be able to use technical documentation; exactly observe the rules of safety and occupational health, to perform any assigned work creatively, demonstrating intellectual initiative.

Shaping of work culture is a very important and multifaceted issue. The state standard of the educational area «Technologies» one of the main objectives of preparing the younger generation for life defines the formation of the youth culture, developing their creative skills, rational management of the household, education of responsibility for results of own activities, of a complex of personal qualities, necessary to the person as a subject of modern production and cultural development of society [3].

The issue of formation of students' work culture in the modern fast-paced society is especially important. Qualitative changes in society, the transition to the new curriculum dictate the need for training of the creative people with unconventional views on life problems, skills of research work, which is able to solve new tasks that require from the students the development of the creative potential.

Thus, analyzing the above, we can determine the approximate scheme of preparation of high school graduates: knowledge of the main provisions of labor legislation, rights and responsibilities in the workplace; attainments of self-service; respectful attitude to the products of human activity; observance of safety rules in the work and aesthetic labor; the possession of practical skills of vocational activity, formation of clear ideas about the world of modern professions, about their capabilities to master different types of professional activities; legal literacy on labor, professional activity; awareness about the general situation in the labor market, trends in employment, the difficulties of professional adaptation at the beginning of employment; possession of practical skills of professional activity; computer skills, ability to use information sources on the issues of professional self-determination independently; the ability for the conscious professional self-determination according to their personal capabilities, abilities and interests.

Educational goals of values related to the work of graduate students (goal, objectives, tasks): education of a civilized host who deliberately refers to labor as the highest value of man and society in conditions of market relations; discipline, organization, ability to engage in industrial relations; education; personal qualities: self-organization, leadership, thrift, initiative, efficiency, discipline, vision of the perspective; arming of the students with theoretical knowledge, practical skills and abilities of work culture, the development of the abilities for a specific activity; formation of a new economic thinking, willingness to act creatively, to apply the received knowledge in practice; to build the understanding of the general principles of modern production, the desire to expand their horizons, to master the general labor culture; the formation of enterprise competence and culture, skills to run the household; education of conscious attitude to the choice of the future profession in the conditions of market relations; the development of the economic roles and positions through the role games by the students in the modern world; education of psychological readiness to work (positive attitude to work, ability to quick adaptation to the new working conditions).

Analyzing the above, we can conclude that the level of work culture of the individual will be higher with the better labor preparation and will reflect the changes that occur in science and the production of modern dynamic society, and the secondary school and the higher school will form a system of qualities that educate a creative, comprehensively developed personality, because creativity is a sign of true culture and prepare them so that they are able to apply their knowledge in practice, to navigate the modern workplace and to adapt quickly to its changes.

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ТИТАРЕНКО В., САВЕНКО И.

КУЛЬТУРА ТРУДА КАК СОСТАВЛЯЮЩАЯ КУЛЬТУРЫ ЛИЧНОСТИ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ ТРУДОВОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ

В статье охарактеризирована культура труда как одна из составляющих культуры человека, рассмотрена важность трудовой подготовки в формировании культуры труда учащегося. Рассмотрены различные научные подходы современных ученых к понятию «культура труда»; обозначены основные идеи трудового воспитания выдающихся украинских педагогов А.С. Макаренко и В.А. Сухомлинского, актуальные в современной педагогической практике. Определены основные векторы формирования культуры труда, обоснованные государственным стандартом образовательной отрасли «Технологии», что позволяют определить структуру подготовки будущего учителя технологий и наполнить рынок труда компетентными специалистами, способными обеспечивать качественный процесс трудового обучения, что будет содействовать формированию культуры труда школьников.

Ключевые слова: культура, культура труда, личность, технологическое образование.

TYTARENKO V., SAVENKO I.

WORK CULTURE AS A COMPONENT OF FUTURE LABOUR TEACHERS' CULTURE

Work culture as one of the components of human culture is described in this article, the importance of work training in the formation of student work culture is outlined. The article describes the culture of labor as one of the components of the human culture, outlining the importance of labor training in shaping the student's work culture. Different scientific approaches of modern scholars to the notion "culture of labor" are considered.

The main ideas of labor education of the outstanding Ukrainian teachers A.S. Makarenko, V.O. Sukhomlinsky are outlined which are relevant in modern pedagogical practice. The main vectors of the formation of a culture of work based on the state standard of the educational branch of «Technologies» are determined, which allows to determine the structure of the training of the future teacher of technologies and to provide the labor market with qualitative specialists who will be able to provide a qualitative process of labor education, which will contribute to the formation of the culture of work of schoolchildren.

It is figured out that the solution of this problem the society traditionally imposes on a secondary school because the pedagogical higher education performs a cultural function, which involves updating the content on the basis of its humanitarization, purposeful use of the achievements of Ukrainian culture. Numerous scientific publications that have appeared in recent years suggest that the search for solution of cultural problems of modern education is gradually gaining wide scope. The purpose of this article is to consider the work culture as an integral part of the culture of the individual.

Thus, the author presumes that education of the person's culture takes the whole life. The main burden of implementing the model of the fully developed person's culture, of course, rests with the school. The primary source of the formation of the culture of the child is the family, which lays the basic components of cultural identity. This happens in the course of the observations the members of the family, their relations to the society in general, and inclusion of the child in the process of vital activity of the family. Education should help people to identify its main values, to internalize moral norms, everyday ethics, namely to understand everyday culture formation.

Keywords: culture, work culture, personality, technological education.

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